

School-Family-Community Partnerships and Student Interaction

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Sarangani District of Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2024-2025. Research instruments on school-family-community partnerships and student interaction were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the study found to exhibit a very high level of school-family-community partnerships, there is a very high level of student interaction, there is a significant relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction. This implies that the higher the school-family-community partnerships, the higher is the student interaction. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction was rejected.

Keywords: school-family-community partnerships and student interaction, school administration and supervision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Student interaction is a critical factor in the learning process, impacting academic achievement, personal growth, and long-term success. Defined broadly as the level of interest, curiosity, and active participation that students exhibit in their educational experience, engagement serves as both a precursor and a predictor of positive educational outcomes. Research has consistently shown that engaged students are more likely to achieve higher academic performance, develop a love for learning, and cultivate skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and self-regulation. Conversely, disengagement often correlates with absenteeism, lower academic achievement, and increased dropout rates, underscoring the importance of understanding and addressing the factors that influence student engagement (Epstein, 2019).

Student engagement in the classroom determines their interest in the subject matter or in the class discussion. Teachers should ensure that they get the full attention of the students to keep them engaged in the lesson. However, teachers complain that there are students who do not participate in the group works while others draw on their notes just when the teachers explain the lesson. More so, there are students who do not submit class requirements, projects, and themes. Oftentimes, teachers complain of the poor engagement in the class as these students perform low in their academic performance (Sargeant, 2014).

Students in the classroom have low student interaction. Teachers observe that there are students struggle to find intrinsic motivation, especially if they do not see the relevance of the material to their own lives or goals. These students less likely to participate in the class activities. This has affected their academic proficiency which affect learning interaction in the classroom (Provinzano, Riley, Levine & Grant, 2018).

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More so, these teachers noted that there are also students who have little say in their learning process, they feel disconnected or uninvested in the material. This leaves the teachers to make sound innovations in their teaching strategies to capture the interest of the students and eventually increase student interaction (Johnston, Engberg, Opper, ontag-Padilla & Xenakis, 2020).

On the other hand, school-family-community partnership is seen by most educators as one driving force that helps improve student engagement in the classroom. They believe that the more parents become involved and take active partnership in school activities, the teachers become more dynamic in their instruction while students become more engaged. This makes school head give enough attention to involve parents in the shared responsibilities in the education of their school children (Castrechini & London, 2012).

Presently, there are limited researches that point out to the relationship between school-family-community partnership and student engagement in the local context. This makes the study different from any other researchers conducted in different settings.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study is aimed to find out the relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. What is the level of school-family-community partnerships in terms of:
 - 1.1. improving communication;
 - 1.2. promoting positive parenting;
 - 1.3. enhancing student learning;
 - 1.4 increasing volunteerism;
 - 1.5 supporting decision-making and advocacy, and
 - 1.6 collaborating with the community?
2. What is the level of level of student engagement in terms of:
 - 2.1 affective engagement;
 - 2.2 learning how to learn;
 - 2.3 behavioral engagement, and
 - 2.4 cognitive engagement?
3. Is there a significant relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was treated at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative correlational design is a type of non-experimental research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables. This study will find out the significance of the relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of school-family-community partnerships and student interaction.

Pearson r. This was used to determine the significance of the relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of School-Family-Community Partnerships

Shown in Table 1 is the level of school-family-community partnerships with an overall mean of 4.11 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, collaborating with the community has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.14 or very high, improving communication, 4.12 or very high; promoting positive parenting, 4.11 or very high; enhancing student learning, 4.12 or very high; increasing volunteerism, 4.11 or very high; and supporting decision-making and advocacy, 4.10 or very high.

Table I. Level of School-Family-Community Partnerships

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Improving Communication	4.12	Very High
Promoting Positive Parenting	4.11	Very High
Enhancing Student Learning	4.12	Very High
Increasing Volunteerism	4.11	Very High
Supporting Decision-Making and Advocacy	4.10	Very High
Collaborating with the Community	4.14	Very High
Overall	4.11	Very High

The result of the study is in consonance with the findings of Epstein (2019) stated that the relationship between school and family is a foundational aspect of a child's educational experience. Effective collaboration between these two institutions has been shown to positively affect student outcomes, including academic achievement, social behavior, and emotional well-being. The relationship between schools and families is a crucial determinant of student success and well-being. When educators and parents work together, they create a powerful support system that nurtures children's growth academically, socially, and emotionally. Investing in strong, respectful, and inclusive school-family relationships is not only beneficial for students, it is essential for building thriving educational communities.

Level of Student Interaction

Shown in Table 2 is the level of student interaction with an overall mean of 4.11 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, extra-curricular activities have the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.13 or very high, liking for school, 4.12 or very high, liking for learning, 4.11 or very high, cognitive engagement, 4.10 or very high, and effort and persistent, 4.09 or very high.

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Table II. Level of Student Interaction

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Liking for Learning	4.11	Very High
Liking for School	4.12	Very High
Effort and Persistence	4.09	Very High
Extra-Curricular Activities	4.13	Very High
Cognitive Engagement	4.10	Very High
Overall	4.11	Very High

The result of the study is aligned with the view of Gardner (2019) and Harper (2018) who stressed that student interaction in the classroom plays a crucial role in shaping a dynamic and effective learning environment. Beyond absorbing facts and completing assignments, students benefit significantly from engaging with their peers through discussion, collaboration, and shared learning experiences. Active interaction helps deepen understanding, develop critical thinking skills, and promote social and emotional growth. This is also supported by the idea of Pennings, Brekelmans, Sadler, Claessens, van der Want & van Tartwijk (2018) who stated that one of the key benefits of student interaction is enhanced learning and comprehension. When students explain concepts to one another, ask questions, or work together on tasks, they are actively processing information rather than passively receiving it.

Significance on the Relationship between School-Family-Community Partnerships and Student Interaction

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.308 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction is rejected.

Table III. Significance on the Relationship between School-Family-Community Partnerships and Student Interaction

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	School-Family-Community Partnerships and Student Interaction	0.308	0.000	Reject

The result of the study is in congruence with the statement of Balwant (2018) who believed that in the evolving field of education, success is no longer the sole responsibility of schools. The active involvement of families and communities has become essential in creating supportive and inclusive learning environments. School-family-community partnerships form a powerful alliance that not only enhances student achievement but also significantly strengthens student interaction, both inside and outside the classroom.

This is also supported by the statement of Reschly & Christenson (2022) who posited that the relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction is deeply intertwined. These partnerships create a supportive framework that enhances student engagement, promotes collaboration, and encourages meaningful connections. When schools, families, and communities work together, they not only strengthen academic outcomes but also nurture the social and interpersonal development of every student.

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a very high level of school-family-community partnerships. This means that the provisions relating to school-family-community partnerships is always manifested.

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The study revealed a very high level of student interaction. This indicates that the provisions relating to student interaction are embodied in the item is always manifested.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction. This implies that the higher the school-family-community partnerships, the higher is the student interaction. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between school-family-community partnerships and student interaction was rejected.

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